

SCENARIO PLANNING FOR COMPANY PERFORMANCE IMPROVEMENT THROUGH OPTIMIZED INNOVATOR MANAGEMENT PRACTICE : A CASE STUDY AT PUPUK INDONESIA GROUP

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Abstract

This study concludes that, in general, the Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and Learning Agility of innovators at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and its subsidiaries are in the very good category. Innovators demonstrate strong motivation in maintaining operational efficiency, high levels of work engagement with the company, and solid learning capabilities derived from data and technical experience. Nevertheless, several challenges remain, including operational complexity, fluctuations in work energy due to daily workloads, and the need to strengthen capabilities in dealing with unstructured and strategic changes. The results of statistical testing indicate that Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and Learning Agility have a significant effect on Innovator Work Productivity. This study also finds that Innovator Work Productivity has a significant effect on Corporate Performance, indicating that innovator productivity plays an important role in driving overall corporate performance. Furthermore, Innovator Work Productivity is proven to mediate the influence of Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and Learning Agility on Corporate Performance, underscoring the strategic role of innovators as key drivers of corporate performance. In anticipation of future dynamic changes, this study has developed four scenario planning alternatives that can be utilized by the company to address potential changes in innovator productivity and corporate performance conditions. The study also provides recommendations for company management to optimize the innovator management function within the organization.

Keywords: *Corporate performance, work engagement, learning agility, work motivation, innovator management, and work productivity.*

INTRODUCTION

In an era of increasingly complex global competition, Human Resources (HR) are no longer viewed as a cost burden, but rather as a strategic asset that plays a crucial role in determining a company's success. HR has the ability to drive innovation and create sustainable added value for the company. Sollosy, Marc *et al.* (2016) state that HR is a dynamic and *intangible capability* that can support the achievement of organizational goals through innovation as a competitive advantage. In line with this, Plaskoff and Josh (2017) emphasize that HR plays a crucial role in driving innovation and improving organizational performance. Therefore, the active involvement of HR in finding solutions to company problems is a crucial aspect that needs to be managed strategically and sustainably in the company. Human resources, specifically employees who feel involved and appreciated, will be more motivated to contribute to organizational performance. Widiartanto, Ajeng Tria Jayanti Wulandari (2019) explained that employee empowerment has a significant impact on company performance. They also explained that *self-efficacy* and good compensation for employees influence employee performance in the company. These factors are examples of work motivation that can drive work productivity in the company. Kaswan (2021) explained that employees with high work motivation tend to be more productive and have better performance. Work motivation itself can come from within (internal) or from outside (external). This is in line with Hasibuan (2003), who explained that both types of work motivation play an important role in increasing employee work productivity. In addition to work motivation, employee engagement in a company also plays a significant role in employee productivity. Gallie and Duncan (2021) explain that there is a positive relationship between employee engagement and employee productivity in a company. Shaufeli *et al.* (2005) also explain that employee engagement is a theoretical construct that can encourage employee productivity in a company through the presence of the dimensions of *Vigor*, *Dedication*, and *Absorption* in the

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employee. In addition to the causal relationship between motivation and work engagement on employee productivity, employee *learning agility* also influences employee productivity in the company. Subekti (2025) explains that employees with high *learning agility* have a tendency to be productive through assignments in participating in innovation activities. In addition, Frissandy (2025) also explains that employees are needed who are able to learn independently and quickly to be able to solve problems and provide solutions to these problems in the company. Rahmani et al. (2023) also explained that *Learning Agility* is a *valid and reliable predictor* for determining *High Potential Leaders*. Individuals with high *Learning Agility* will easily learn new things and increase Work Productivity in the Company. Ashriyana, Rezki et al. (2024) also explained that *Learning Agility* is an individual's willingness and ability to be able to engage in active learning in order to adapt activity opportunities from experience and apply learning to perform successfully in new situations and conditions, as well as changes in the Company. Based on the information above, it is known that there is a causal relationship between Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and *Learning Agility* of employees on Work Productivity of employees in the company. Speaking of Work Productivity, there is a causal relationship between employee Work Productivity and Company Productivity through increased employee learning within the Company. Employees who actively engage in learning to improve their competencies significantly impact Company Performance through their ability to act actively, adaptively, flexibly, and focus on solving Company problems in the future (SO 2019). Nosike et al. (2022) also explain that there is a positive relationship between Work Motivation and the work environment on employee Work Productivity and Company Performance. In line with this, PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) also consistently strives to improve its performance year after year. This is evident in the company's operating revenue and net profit data from 2015 to 2024, as shown in the graph below:

The company has successfully maintained its commitment to continuously improve its Company Performance from year to year (Personal 2024). A glimpse of PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero), this Company is the largest fertilizer producer in Asia which is a company owned by the Republic of Indonesia. PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) is a holding Company that oversees 9 Subsidiaries in Indonesia with a market share of PSO (*Public Service Obligation*) fertilizer products for Farmers in Indonesia, as well as an international market share for Non-PSO (*Non-Public Service Obligation*) fertilizer products. Sutrisno (2024) also explained that " *PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) managed to enter the 71st rank in the list of the 500 best ASEAN companies according to Fortune Southeast Asia 500 thanks to revenues of IDR 79.21 T in 2023. He also explained that this success is the result of the hard work and innovation of the entire Pupuk Indonesia Team which also contributes to national food security.*" Pribadi (2024) in Sutrisno (2024) also explained that " *PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) managed to record revenue and savings of Rp 1.3 T from employee innovation contributions. He also explained that this value was an innovation contribution consisting of Rp 1.2 T from increased efficiency or savings and Rp 0.1 T from increased revenue. He also explained that based on the 2023 Annual Report, Pupuk Indonesia managed to occupy the seventh largest position in the world in the fertilizer industry. He reiterated that this was inseparable from innovation which had a direct impact on profitability*". Despite having good achievements such as the data above, PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) continues to remain committed to improving Company Performance considering that there are greater challenges in the future to be able to realize this Company as " *a leading global agrosolution and integrated chemical company* " (Subekti 2025). This can also be seen from the Performance data of fertilizer Companies in the world, where PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) is still not ranked among the top 3 (three) fertilizer companies in the world. The 3 (three) largest fertilizer companies in the world are as follows:

Table 1 Table of net profits of the 3 (three) largest fertilizer companies in the world

No.	Company	Country	Net Profit After Tax (\$ Billion)	Net Profit After Tax (Rp Trillion)
1	Wesfarmers	Australia	\$2.60	Rp. 42.87
2	Saudi Arabian Fertilizer Company	Saudi Arabia	\$2.10	Rp. 34.63
3	Nutrients	Canada	\$0.70	Rp. 11.54
	Indonesian Fertilizer	Indonesia	-	Rp. 8.89

Information :

Processed based on the exchange rate of 1 USD to Rupiah (Rp) as of August 2, 2025

From the data above, we can see that there is still a high Performance Gap between the achievements obtained by Pupuk Indonesia in 2024 and the achievements obtained by the 3 (three) other major competing companies, so that the commitment to continue improving Company Performance in the future is an important thing to pay attention to in encouraging and realizing the Company's Vision to become " a leading global agrosolution and integrated chemical company : In addition, Ruky (2025) explains that " there are challenges being faced by the Company, especially in innovation management, namely the need to optimize the number and quality of more strategic innovations to be able to drive the Company's Financial Performance . Innovation in the Company is mostly carried out by Middle Management, so that Financial Performance in the Company has not been optimally achieved by the company". Subekti, Frissandy, and Arjangi (2025) also explain that " appropriate Innovator Management is needed to become a System that can form an Innovation Culture so that it can encourage Innovators at all levels of office, especially at the Leader level in the company".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Work Motivation

Purnama *et al.* (2021) explain that motivation is one of the factors that can influence a person's behavior. Motivation is also known as a driving force, desire, or support that can make someone enthusiastic and motivated to work better, so that they can act in accordance with the best ways aimed at leading that person in an optimal direction. According to Hasibuan (2007) in Purnama, Riansyah Rainal (2021) explains that the origin of the word motivation is *movemore* (Latin) which means encouragement or movement. Motivation in a company is only intended for human resources (HR) in general and implementing employees in particular. Motivation guides how to direct the potential of implementing employees to want to work more productively together so that they succeed in achieving and realizing the goals set by the Company/Management. Kartono (1985) in Hartuti (2002) also explains that motivation (from the Latin word, *motivus*) means the cause, reason, and basic thought, the drive for someone to act or the main idea that always influences human behavior. Manullang in Hartuti (2022) explains that motivation is a factor that drives someone to do or act in a certain way, and work motivation is something that provides encouragement or enthusiasm for work.

Work Engagement

Khan (1990), in Kular (2008) explains *Work Engagement* as the process of utilizing the self of organizational members in their roles in work. Employees who have *Work Engagement* will express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during work. Khan 1990 in Kular 2008 explains the physical aspect of *Work Engagement* is the physical energy of employees in completing tasks, while the cognitive aspect is employee trust in the organization, both in leaders and working conditions. The last aspect is the emotional aspect, namely the employee's feelings about each factor whether they have a positive or negative attitude towards the leader and the organization.

Learning Agility

Ashriyana, Rezki *et al.* (2024) explain that *Learning Agility* is an individual's willingness and ability to engage in active learning in order to adapt to activity opportunities from experience, and apply that learning to perform successfully in new and changing situations and conditions, especially in improving *organizational agility*. *Learning*

Agility consists of four dimensions, namely *people agility*, *results agility*, *mental agility* and *change agility*.

Company performance

Elfian (2023) explains that company performance can be assessed through financial performance. Financial performance is the results or achievements achieved by company management in effectively managing company assets over a specific period. Financial performance is generally described using financial ratios, including profitability ratios. Profitability ratios illustrate a company's ability to generate profits.

Employee Work Productivity

Abdelwahed *et al.* (2023) explain that employee productivity is the productivity of the workforce, which can be evaluated by how much work can be delivered within a specified time. The following is the difference between employee productivity and employee work performance according to Abdelwahed *et al.*

Research Hypothesis

In relation to the conceptual research model above, the following hypothesis can be put forward:

- (1) It is suspected that the existing conditions related to Work Motivation, Work Engagement, *Learning Agility* , Innovator Productivity are good in the Company's Performance Improvement Scenario Planning.
- (2) It is suspected that Work Motivation, Work Engagement, *Learning Agility* , Innovator Productivity have a direct and indirect influence on improving company performance.

METHOD

Time and Location of Research

This research will be conducted over three months, from July to September 2025, at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and its subsidiaries. PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) is located in Jakarta as a *holding company* , with the following subsidiaries located:

- PT Pupuk Kalimantan Timur = Bontang, East Kalimantan
- PT Petrokimia Gresik = Gresik, East Java
- PT Pupuk Kujang = Cikampek, West Java
- PT Pupuk Sriwidjaja Palembang = Palembang, South Sumatra
- PT Pupuk Iskandar Muda = Lhokseumawe, Aceh
- PT Pupuk Indonesia Support = Jakarta
- PT Pupuk Indonesia Niaga = Jakarta
- PT Pupuk Indonesia Logistics = Jakarta
- PT Pupuk Indonesia Pangan = Jakarta

Sampling Determination Method

The population in the study was all employees in the Pupuk Indonesia Group environment in 2025, namely 7,750 organic employees with the following employee details:

Figure 2 1organic employees of PI Group

The process of determining the sample size based on the population size uses the Isaac and Michael formula

(Sugiyono 2015 in Yusuf 2024). The formula used is as follows:

$$S = \frac{\lambda^2 \cdot N \cdot P \cdot Q}{d^2 (N-1) + \lambda^2 \cdot P \cdot Q}$$

Figure 2 Research sample formula

Information:

S = Number of samples

λ^2 = Degree of freedom 1 and error 10%, then chi square = 2.706 (chi square table)

N = Population size

P = Probability of correct (0.5) Q = Probability of incorrect (0.5)

D = Difference between the sample mean and the population mean with bias difference 0.05, 0.05, 0.1

$$S = \frac{2.706 \times 7750 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{0.05 \times 0.05 (7750-1) + 2.706 \times 2.706 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}$$

$$S = \frac{5.242.875}{19.3725 + 1.831}$$

$$S = \frac{5.242.875}{21.2035}$$

$$S = 247,264 = 247 \text{ or } \pm 250 \text{ people.}$$

Based on the research sample calculation above, the sample size for this study was 250 individuals within PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and its subsidiaries. The sampling technique used *purposive sampling*, with the sample criteria determined by the researcher, namely employees who have actively implemented innovation in the company over the past two years.

Data collection using the TAIDA analysis approach

The data collection process using the TAIDA approach to obtain the right strategy is carried out using *the In-Depth Interview method*. The data collection pattern uses a question and answer method. The researcher asks several questions to the informants, and the interview results are summarized and sorted and analyzed to obtain a strategy in the TAIDA analysis approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structural Model Analysis (Inner Model)

The structural model evaluation stage (*Inner Model*) consists of a *model fit* test and a hypothesis test. Partial hypothesis testing is conducted by observing the significance of the relationships between variables (*Direct* and *Indirect Effects*). The results of the *bootstrapping process* on the structural model can be seen in the following figure:

Source: SmartPLS 2025 Output

Figure 1 Results of the bootstrapping process

a. R Square

R-Square value or coefficient of determination shows the diversity of endogenous constructs that can be explained by exogenous constructs simultaneously. The results of the R Square analysis are presented in the following table:

Table 1 R Square Results

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Work Productivity	0.501	0.496
Company performance	0.444	0.436

Source: Primary Data Processed by PLS, 2025

R Square Value Based on Table 4.12 above, the R-square value is 0.501 . This value is interpreted to mean that the variables of Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and Learning Agility contribute 50.1% to Work

Productivity. While the remaining 49.9% of Work Productivity is influenced by other factors. In company performance, the R-square value of 0.444 means that Work Motivation, Work Engagement, *Learning Agility* , and Work Productivity contribute 44.4% to Company Performance, while the remaining 55.6% is influenced by other factors.

b. Model Equation

Following this is results model equation Which obtained in study This through *innermodel* :

Table 2 Results of the model equation

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>
Work Motivation -> Work Productivity	0.156
Work Engagement -> Work Productivity	0.140
Learning Agility -> Work Productivity	0.528
Motivation -> Company Performance	0.116
Engagement -> Company Performance	0.262
Learning Agility -> Company Performance	0.166
Productivity -> Company Performance	0.265

Source: Primary Data Processed by PLS, 2025

- 1) Work Productivity in this study is influenced by three variables, namely Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and *Learning Agility* . The results of the equation obtained are as follows:

$$PK = 0.156 MK + 0.140 KK + 0.528 LA$$

Information :

- PK = Work productivity
- MK = Work Motivation
- KK = Work engagement
- LA = *Learning agility*

The Work Motivation coefficient value of 0.156 means that for every 1 unit increase in motivation, Work Productivity will increase by 0.156 units assuming other variables remain constant. Furthermore, the Work Engagement Variable has a coefficient of 0.140 meaning that for every 1 unit increase in Work Engagement, Work Productivity will increase by 0.140 units assuming other variables remain constant. *The Learning Agility variable* has a coefficient of 0.528 meaning that for every 1 unit increase in *Learning Agility* , Work Productivity will increase by 0.528 units assuming other variables remain constant.

- 2) In this study, company performance was influenced by four variables: work motivation, work engagement, *learning agility* , and work productivity. The resulting equation is as follows:

$$KP = 0.116 MK + 0.262 KK + 0.166 LA + 0.265 PK$$

Information :

- KP = Company performance
- MK = Work Motivation
- KK = Work engagement
- LA = *Learning agility*
- PK = Work productivity

The Work Motivation coefficient value of 0.116 means that for every 1 unit increase in Work Motivation, Company Performance will increase by 0.116 units, assuming other variables remain constant. Furthermore, the Work Engagement variable has a coefficient of 0.262. means that for every 1 unit increase in Work Engagement, Company Performance will increase by 0.262 units assuming other variables remain constant. *The Learning Agility variable* has a coefficient of 0.166, meaning that for every 1 unit increase in

Learning Agility, Company Performance will increase by 0.166 units assuming other variables remain constant. On the Work Productivity variable, a coefficient of 0.265 is obtained, meaning that for every 1 unit increase in Work Productivity, Company Performance will increase by 0.265 units assuming other variables remain constant.

c. Hypothesis Test Results

1) Descriptive Hypothesis Testing

The descriptive hypotheses presented in this study are Work Motivation, Work Engagement, *Learning Agility*, and Work Productivity, with Company Performance as the first hypothesis in the study. Based on the descriptive analysis, the following results were obtained:

Table 3 Descriptive hypothesis test

Item	Average Item	Percentage	Information
Work motivation	4.76	79.4%	Very good
Work Engagement	4.84	80.6%	Very good
Learning Agility	4.69	78.1%	Very good
Work Productivity	3.64	60.6%	Good
Company performance	4.18	69.6%	Good

The results in Table 4 above show that Work Motivation, Work Engagement, *Learning Agility*, Work Productivity, and Company Performance have average values greater than 2.66–3.49, or 44.33–58.17%. Therefore, the first hypothesis in this study is accepted.

2) Statistical Hypothesis

This statistical analysis was conducted by comparing the *T-table value* with the *T-statistic value* generated from *bootstrapping results* in PLS. The influence between variables is considered significant at the 5% level if the *T-statistic value* is greater than the *T-table*. with a significance level of 0.05, namely 1.96. The results of the t-statistic values are presented as follows:

Table 4 Statistical hypothesis testing

2).a Direct Influence

	T-Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Work Motivation -> Work Productivity	2,312	0.021
Work Engagement -> Work Productivity	2,144	0.032
<i>Learning Agility</i> -> Work Productivity	10,421	0,000
Motivation -> Company performance	2,308	0.021
Engagement -> Company Performance	4,372	0,000
<i>Learning Agility</i> -> Company Performance	3,375	0.001
Productivity -> Company Performance	5,768	0,000

2).b Indirect Influence

	<i>T-Statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P Values</i>
Engagement -> Productivity -> Company Performance	2,047	0.041
Learning Agility -> Productivity -> Company Performance	4,851	0,000
Motivation -> Productivity -> Company Performance	2,239	0.026

Bootstrapping process can be seen in Table 5 explains that Work Motivation has a t-value of 2.312 > 1.960 and a significance value of 0.021 < 0.05, which means that Work Motivation has an effect on Work Productivity. The results of the analysis show that Work Engagement has an effect on Work Productivity . This is evidenced by the t-value of 2.144 > 1.960 with a significance of 0.032 < 0.05. T-value *Learning Agility* to Work Productivity was 10.421 > 1.960 with a significance of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This indicates that *Learning Agility* has an effect on Work Productivity . Based on these results, it can be concluded that the hypothesis stating that there is an influence of Work Motivation (ϵ 1), Work Engagement (ϵ 2), *Learning Agility* (ϵ 3) on Innovator Productivity (η 1) in the Company is accepted by the results of empirical research. The test results of the influence of Work Motivation on Company Performance obtained a t-value of 2.308 > 1.960 and a significance value of 0.021 < 0.05, which means that Work Motivation has an effect on Company Performance. Furthermore, in the Work Engagement Variable, there is an influence of Work Engagement on Company Performance . This is evidenced by the t-value of 4.372 > 1.960 with a significance of 0.000 < 0.05. T-value *Learning Agility* to Company performance is 3.375 > 1.960 with a significance of 0.00 , which is less than 0.05. This indicates that *Learning Agility* has an effect on Company Performance . Thus, the hypothesis in this study which states that there is an influence of Work Motivation (ϵ 1) , Work Engagement (ϵ 2) , *Learning Agility* (ϵ 3) on Company Performance (η 2) is accepted. The Productivity variable shows that there is an influence of Work Productivity on Company Performance as evidenced by the calculated t value of 5.768 > 1.960 and a significance value of 0.000 < 0.05. Based on these results, it can be concluded that the hypothesis stating that there is an influence of Innovator Work Productivity (η 1) on Company Performance (η 2). is accepted by the results of empirical research. Indirect influence shows the hypothesis stating that there is an influence of Work Motivation (ϵ 1) , Work Engagement (ϵ 2) , *Learning Agility* (ϵ 3) on Company Performance (η 2) through Innovator Work Productivity (η 1) accepted by the results of empirical research. This is proven by the calculated t value > 1.960 and a significance value < 0.05.

Discussion

The Existing Condition of Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and *Learning Agility* of Innovators on Work Productivity of Innovators at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and its Subsidiaries

The results of this study indicate that Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and Work Productivity at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and its Subsidiaries are in the fairly good category. This indicates that the Company has an adequate foundation and Human Resources (HR) management system, but there is still significant room for improvement. Motivation consists of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. The "Fairly Good" category implies that motivation is not yet fully optimal. Some innovators may still see innovation as an additional task rather than an integral part of their daily work, resulting in a mid-level of internal drive. This motivation is sufficient to generate routine innovations (e.g., minor process improvements), but may not be strong enough to trigger breakthrough *innovations* that require significantly greater risk and time commitment. Employees at Pupuk Indonesia Group generally demonstrate stable levels of Dedication and Vigor because they understand the Company's strategic role in national food security. This generates a fundamental commitment that keeps *their* engagement *above the* low average. This engagement allows innovators to participate in established innovation programs, but they may not consistently seek out opportunities for *proactive engagement* or fully utilize their intellectual resources outside of formal direction. Existing innovation *output* is sufficient to keep the Company competitive and operationally efficient, but global competitive pressures and sustainability demands demand a surge in productivity toward the Very Good level. *Learning Agility* variable is in the good category. *Learning Agility* is a person's ability to learn from experience and

then apply those lessons to successful performance in new or first-time situations. It is a key predictor of success in roles that require innovation and rapid adaptation. *Learning Agility* serves as a force multiplier for innovation efforts. Innovators at Pupuk Indonesia Group who are agile in learning will be more productive, able to produce solutions that are not only efficient but also relevant and adaptive to the future of the fertilizer industry.

Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and *Learning Agility* of Innovators on Work Productivity of Innovators at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and its Subsidiaries

Based on the research that has been conducted, the results show that Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and *Learning Agility* of innovators on Innovator Work Productivity at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and its Subsidiaries. This is proven by the calculated t value $> t$ table and a significance value < 0.05 . Innovator work productivity at Pupuk Indonesia can be defined as the ability of employees to produce new solutions—whether it is process efficiency in the factory, development of new fertilizer products, or optimization of business models—which provide significant added value for the Company and the Country. Work Motivation is “the driving force, cause, basic thoughts, factors, and needs that can influence a person’s behavior, making them enthusiastic, energetic, and have the energy to work better and more productively, thereby achieving and realizing the goals set by the Company Management. Motivation serves as the initial fuel that drives innovators to go beyond their daily tasks. The results of the study indicate a significant influence of work motivation on work productivity. This is supported by previous research conducted by Mirdas, Muhammad Sobah (2016) which showed that motivational factors that have a strong relationship with employee work motivation are the relationship between superiors and subordinates, working conditions, employee development, and the work itself. High motivation ensures that innovators not only generate ideas but also persist in implementing those ideas until they are successfully integrated into factory operations or the market.

Lockwood (2007) explains that *work engagement* is the way employees commit to something or someone within an organization. He also explains that how hard people work within a company and how long they stay with a company depends on their commitment to the organization. Hypothesis testing results show that work engagement influences work productivity. In a heavy industrial environment like Pupuk Indonesia, innovation demands energy. Employees with high *vigor* are less easily fatigued by bureaucratic obstacles or technical challenges encountered in the field. Work Engagement ensures that time spent on innovation results in high-quality and sustainable *output*. The analysis that has been conducted shows that *Learning Agility* has an impact on Work Productivity. Ashriyana, Rezki et al. (2024) explained that *Learning Agility* is an individual's willingness and ability to be able to engage in active learning in order to adapt to activity opportunities from experience, and apply that learning to perform successfully in new and changing situations and conditions, especially in improving *Organizational Agility*. Pupuk Indonesia Group continues to face the need to adopt new technologies (e.g., supply chain digitalization, implementation of global *best practices* in production facilities). Innovators with *Learning Agility* (especially *Mental Agility* and *Change Agility*) are able to master and integrate these technologies much faster. Through *People Agility*, innovators are able to absorb knowledge from various *stakeholders* (suppliers, farmers, other subsidiaries) and integrate it into more holistic solutions (for example, developing *blended fertilizers* that suit the specific needs of land in various regions). Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and Learning Agility will create a work ecosystem that is highly conducive to Innovator Productivity. Motivation provides the basic drive, while Work Engagement ensures emotional commitment and focus, while Learning Agility ensures innovators can continue to adapt and remain relevant amidst rapid industrial changes, resulting in optimal innovation productivity at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and its subsidiaries.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings obtained from the research, the following results can be concluded:

1. The existing condition of work motivation, work engagement, and *learning agility* of innovators towards work productivity of innovators at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and its subsidiaries. Work motivation is in the very good category. good. Innovators are motivated to keep systems running efficiently, but the drive for radical innovation is hampered by operational complexity and potential bureaucracy. Work Engagement is in the excellent category. The Company's dedication is unquestionable, but the quality of energy (*Vigor*) and focus (*Absorption*) can fluctuate, depending on the daily operational load. *Learning Agility* falls into the very good category. Innovators are good at learning from structured data and technical experience, but they need to develop capabilities for new situations involving changes in business models, organizations, or unstructured risks.
2. Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and *Learning Agility* of Innovators on Work Productivity of Innovators at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and Subsidiaries. The results of the study indicate that Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and *Learning Agility* of Innovators on Work Productivity of Innovators at PT Pupuk

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Indonesia (Persero) and Subsidiaries . This is evidenced by the calculated t value > 1.960 and a significance value < 0.05 .

3. Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and *Learning Agility* of Innovators on Company Performance at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and Subsidiaries . The results of the study indicate that Work Motivation, Work Engagement, and *Learning Agility* of Innovators on Company Performance at PT Pupuk Indonesia (Persero) and Subsidiaries . This is evidenced by the calculated t value > 1.960 and a significance value < 0.05 .
4. There is an influence of Innovator Work Productivity on Company Performance. This is proven by the calculated t value > 1.960 and the significance value < 0.05 .
5. There is an influence of Work Motivation, Work Engagement, *Learning Agility* on Company Performance through Innovator Work Productivity as evidenced by the calculated t value > 1.960 and a significance value < 0.05 .

There are 4 (four) Scenario Plans that have been prepared in case of changes in conditions.

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